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Phytodiversity and indigenous knowledge in coastal line of Rajakamangalam Thurai, Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, India

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ABSTRACT

Ethnobotanical knowledge of the village communities from various ecosystem use largest proportion of biodiversity for human and veterinary healthcare of different organism, medicinal plants have been greatly considered by rural communities as they improve the economy of rural people. India's traditional system of medicine is related to richness of herbal plants biodiversity. The ultimate aim of the study is to document the Angiosperms and their indigenous uses from the coastal line from Periyakadu to Rajakamangalamthurai, which is located in the Rajakamangalam Panchayat of Kanyakumari district in Tamil Nadu. The present study documented as a total 97 taxa distributed in 41 families. Among the 97species 88 plants are dicotyledons and 9 plants are monocotyledons. Family wise distribution shows that Solanaceae is the dominant family represented by 8 species under 5 genera. Of these 97 taxa, 43 (44%) were herbs, 20 (21%) were shrubs, 26 (27%) were trees and 8(8%) were climbers belonging to 39 different families were recorded. Among the 97 plants 88 plants are used as medicine and 26 plants are edible. The plants are also used as fodder, ornamental, timber, dye, oil and Fibre of 14, 10, 7, 6, 1 and 1 species respectively. The various plant parts are used as medicine such as Leaves of 54 plants are used as medicine in various forms for various diseases. It is followed by other parts such as Roots, Fruits, Bark, Flower, Seeds, Stem and Latex of 18, 13, 8, 5, 5, 2 and 2 species respectively. Most of the people in the study area depend on traditional medicine for primary healthcare system. Therefore, conservation Angiosperms is more essential for our future generation.

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INTRODUCTION

Ethnobotanical studies have shown that humans have discovered and improved plants for a variety of purposes including food, shelter and medicine. Even in this case of medicine where modern inventions appear to dominate, we owe a great debt to folk medicine for knowledge of the healing properties of plants (Schultes, 1978).

In traditional medicine, plants are required as a major component to cure many diseases caused by bacteria, fungi and virus in man. The World Health Organization (WHO) has estimated that 80% of the populations of developing countries still rely on traditional medicines mostly plant drugs for their primary health care needs (Jayakumar *et al.*, 2019).

Herbal therapy has come of age and today medicinal plants play a significant role in human healthcare globally. In USA about 25% of all prescriptions dispensed in public pharmacies contain drugs extracted from higher plants are about 64% of the total global populations remains depended on traditional medicine for their healthcare needs. In India alone approximately 7500 medicinal plants are traditionally used against various ailments while Korea, Japan, China and Malaysia together with few other Southeast Asian countries are the other leading in the world in the use of herbal medicines (Kingston *et al.*, 2009).

India has rich plant diversity and is one among the mega biodiversity countries of the world. Indians have been using medicinal plants since antiquity and the Ayurvedic methods date back to 5000 B.C. India is rich in its coastal population from the immemorial time with their traditional knowledge system which deals with the many significant aspects and the health problems of coastal communities. Indigenous knowledge on natural resources, utilization of medicinal plants not exceeding the resilience of the surrounding environment is regarded as an important measure of sustainable plants biodiversity conservation (Kingston *et al.*, 2009).

The therapeutic properties of plants are existing since few thousand years ago. However, use of plants to cure diseases and relieve physical sufferings dates back to the earlier times of mankind's history probably starting from the first moment when a human being or their animal got ill. It is also reported that expeditions, undertaken by those interested in the cultural attributes of primitive societies, obtained valuable information regarding the use of plants for medicine (Muhammad *et al.*, 2014).

Medicinal plants are in use for human health management since ages and still today it is serving the purpose with stability through scientific validity. That means, with the help of modern science plant drug occurrence and quantitative estimation of active principles, alkaloids, terpenoids, phenolics, etc., as per the requirements for management of diseases.

Accordingly, it has created the platform for exploration and identification of medicinal plants in different climatic zones, area, and district and at state level. During exploration in different Northeastern states, it was observed that medicinal plants are categorized in the form belonging to established systems of medicines like Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha, Homoeopathy and modern medicines and secondly, the plants used by local traditional healers provide health services by obtaining locally available herbs from nature (Rama Shanker, 2017).

Coastal vegetation provides habitats, food and fodder for fauna as well as protection from the wave action. Coastal sand is continually being eroded and deposited on the shore by wave action. Therefore, the role of vegetation in dune fixation is critical since, they serve as wind trappers, sand binders and dune stabilizers (Costanza *et al.*, 1997). Tamil Nadu coastal line has a length of about 1076 km; it constitutes about 15% of the total coastal length of India. The coastal zone is an important biogeographically habitats of the Indian subcontinent (Rodgers and Panwar, 1998).

Coastal vegetation contains many species of specific flora and thus it is an ecological store house rich in biodiversity and also has ecological values. The plants are source of food, fodder, medicine, edible oil etc. In this region and they are proving their potential to be cultivated as each crop in many parts of the world. Despite their credentials, these plants had been relatively under explored for exploiting their potential (Muhammad *et al.*, 2014). The coastal plants are also used for construction materials, fuel wood and many other purposes.

The characteristic feature of the coastal zone is high population density dominated by fisherman and coir workers. Coastal sand dunes are formed from wind, tide and wave action. The plants are playing a vital role in protecting the coast from erosion and flooding.

Even today this area holds much more hidden treasure; almost 80% of the information on the uses of plants as traditional medicines has not been documented from different sectors of the district. Keeping this is view, the present study was initiated, with an aim to document the Angiosperms and its indigenous uses including the knowledge of rural people and folklore on the utilization of medicinal plants in remote of Rajakamangalam thurai of Kanyakumari District. Similar types of works were carried out by many authors in different regions of India (Jayakumar and Rejitha, 2022); Ramarajan and Murugesan (2014); Padmavathy and Anbarashan (2011); Das and Kamboj (2020); Sugumaran and Avudainayagam (2017); Vidyasagaran and Madhusoodanan (2014); Uma and Devi Renchu (2022).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Kanyakumari district is commonly referred to as Nanjil Nadu due to its ancient region that once formed a part of the Cheran Kingdom in Tamilakam, primarily known for its fertile lands and extensive agricultural activities. From Periyakadu to Rajakamangalam thurai coastal area comes under

Rajakamangalam panchayat located in Kanyakumari district. It is located approximately 13 kilometers from Nagercoil, which is the administrative headquarters of Kanyakumari District.

The region is notable for the Centre for Marine Science and Technology located in Azhathangarai. Ecologically, the Rajakkamangalam estuary and Azhathangarai marshland are significant for their coastal ecosystems, featuring mangroves, sand dunes and serving as breeding sites for sea turtles. These areas are also habitats for various bird species. Lamore Beach is a serene and picturesque beach located in Rajakkamangalam in the Kanyakumari District of Tamil Nadu. It is an emerging tourist destination known for its tranquil atmosphere and natural beauty, offering visitors a peaceful escape from the bustling city life.

Methods

The present study was conducted in the wild plants used for medical purpose by the local communities in their traditional health care system and to assess the status of medicinal plant diversity around Periyakadu to Rajakamangalam thurai coastal area of Kanyakumari district.

Intensive surveys carried out to collect data on indigenous knowledge on uses of medicinal plants and phytodiversity practices by local communities of villages in an around the present study area. The target groups were interviewed based on their occupation which includes medicinal plant collections, practitioners and local farmers.

Data collection

A survey was conducted randomly in the study area at different distance gradients from Periyakadu to shoreline of the Rajakamangalam thurai. The data collection includes plant collection, herbarium preparation and ethnobotanical survey. Plant collection was done by direct visit to coastline, and the specimens were properly tagged and noted important characters in the field note book. Information are collected from the local people,

traditional healers and herbal dealers regarding the indigenous uses by interview method and include questions about famous church and believes, medicinal uses of plants in coastline, part of plant used, mode of preparation, mode of application and other uses of the plant. All the information received from the respondents was recorded. GPS photographs were shown to the traditional healers for better understanding instead and the collected plant specimens were made into herbarium and deposited into STHC herbarium, Department of P.G and Research centre of Botany S.T Hindu college, Nagercoil. The collected specimens were identified with the help of local floras like Flora of Presidency of Madras (Gamble and Fisher 1915) and an Excursion flora of Central Carnatic Tamilnadu (Mathew, 1983) and also with help of experts for plant identification. Some of the medicinal information were collected from the available pertinent literature and Google search engine (The Botanical survey of India).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ecosystem of coastal villages is rich in important medicinal plant species. The plants are not only valuable as herbal drugs but also significant as a source of food, fodder, spices etc. The ethno botanical informations are gathered from the Rajakamangalam thurai coastal village.

The present exploration on indigenous uses of Angiosperms of Rajakamangalam thurai coastal area has yielded information on 97 plant species. Of these 97 plants, 88 plants are dicotyledons and 9 plants are monocotyledons and the plants are distributed under 88 genera and 41 families. They include herbs, shrubs, trees and climbers. Among 97 taxa, 43 species (44%) were herbs, 20 species (21%) were shrubs, 26 species (27%) trees, 8 species (8%) were climbers and belonging to 41 different families were recorded. The collected plant specimens were tabulated with its binomial, family, local name, useful part, indigenous uses and medicinal uses (Table 1).

Table 1. List of medicinal plants and their Binomial name, local name, family, habit, useful part, indigenous uses and their medicinal uses collected from coastal area of Rajakamangalam thurai

Sl	Botanical name	Family	Habit	Useful part	Indigenous uses	Medicinal uses
1.	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> [L.] Sweet	Malvaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Medicinal	Piles, relief pain
2.	<i>Acacia planifrons</i> [Wight and Arn]	Leguminosae	Tree	Bark and Leaves	Medicinal	Wound healing and reduce inflammation
3.	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Medicinal	Cough, cold and asthma
4.	<i>Achras zapota</i> L.	Sapotaceae	Tree	Fruit and leaves	Medicinal	Cough, cold and diarrhoea
5.	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Root	Medicinal	Kidney stone, urinary disorders
6.	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) ex Schult.	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Whole plant.	Medicinal, ornamental	Kidney stones and flushes out toxin from the urinary tract
7.	<i>Agave vivipara</i> L.	Amaryllidaceae	shrub	Leaves	Medicinal, edible	Digestion, healing ulcers
8.	<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.)	Liliaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Medicinal	Liver detoxification and jaundice
9.	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.).Dc.	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Medicinal	Wounds, skin eruption and rashes
10.	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal	Haemoglobin level, anaemia
11.	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves, Bark and Fruit	Medicinal, timber	Maintaining normal Blood sugar level
12.	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burma.f.) Wall.ex Nees	Acanthaceae	Herb	whole plant	Medicinal, fodder	Fever, body pain and viral infections
13.	<i>Anona muricata</i> L.	Anonaceae	Tree	Leaves and Fruit	Medicinal	Preventing the growth of cancer cells
14.	<i>Anona squamosa</i> L.	Anonaceae	Tree	Whole plant	Medicinal	Diarrhoea
15.	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lam.	Moraceae	Tree	Latex fruit, leaves and	Medicinal, edible,	Wound healing and dental care

			bark	fodder	
16.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss	Meliaceae	Tree	Whole plant	Medicinal Skin Diseases like Eczema and psoriasis
17.	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Edible Reduces swelling and maintain kidney and liver health
18.	<i>Boerhavia erecta</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Medicinal Fatigue and liver function
19.	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Arecaceae	Tree	Whole plant	Medicinal, edible Cough & Respiratory disorders
20.	<i>Brachiaria distachyos</i> (L.)	Poaceae	Herb	Leaves and Stem	Medicinal Fever, detoxify the body
21.	<i>Bulbostylis barbata</i> (Rotta.) C.B Clarke	Cyperaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Medicinal, edible Fever and flush out toxins
22.	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) Dryand	Asclepiadaceae	Shrub	Whole plant	Medicinal, edible Leprosy and ringworm
23.	<i>Cantharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G.Don	Apocynaceae	Shrub	Root and Leaves	Medicinal Fever, wounds and muscle pain
24.	<i>Canthium coromandelicum</i> (Burma.f.) Alston	Rubiaceae	Shrub	Leaves, Bark and Fruit	Timber Indigestion, bloating and acidity
25.	<i>Capsicum annum</i> L.	Solanaceae	Herb	Fruit	Medicinal Relieve pain, arthritis and muscle stiffness
26.	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Sapindaceae	Climber	Fruit and Root	Medicinal, ornamental Joint pain, cough & stomach disorders
27.	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Caricaceae	Tree	Leaves	Medicinal Dengue fever, enhance platelets
28.	<i>Cascabela thevetica</i> (L) Lippold	Apocynaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Medicinal Chronic wound and skin infection
29.	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i> Forster & Forster.f.	Casuarinaceae	Tree	Root and Bark	Medicinal, edible Pimple and dysentery
30.	<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (L.) R.king H.Robinson	Asteraceae	Shrub	Root and Leaves	Medicinal Wounds to stop bleeding
31.	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Capparaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal, ornamental Joint pain, swelling and insect bites
32.	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.	Leguminosae	Climber	Flower and Root	Medicinal Memory, reduce stress and boost immunity
33.	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.	Arecaceae	Tree	Fruit	Edible Body coolant
34.	<i>Coleus amboinicus</i> Lour.	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaves	Timber, dye Cough, cold, asthma and bronchitis
35.	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Commelinaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal, fodder Urinary infection, kidney stone pain
36.	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i> Duchesne	Cucurbitaceae	Climber	Fruit and seed	Medicinal Deep sleep and Reduce stress
37.	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	Herb	Leaves and Root	Medicinal Cough, cramps, dysentery and headache
38.	<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Solanaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Medicinal, fodder Asthma, bronchitis and chest congestion
39.	<i>Dyschoriste madurensis</i> (Burma.f.) Kuntze	Acanthaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal, ornamental Wound healing
40.	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.)	Asteraceae	Herb	Leaves	Edible, timber, coir, Premature graying, strengthens hair roots oil
41.	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Herb	Latex	Edible, dye Warts, ringworm and skin disease
42.	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal Asthma, cough and bronchitis
43.	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Moraceae	Tree	Leaves and Bark	Medicinal, fodder Asthma, constipation, wounds and Ulcers
44.	<i>Gomphrena celosioides</i> Mart.	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Medicinal, timber Cough, Respiratory issues
45.	<i>Gomphrena globosa</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Leaves and Flower	Medicinal, edible Digestion, constipation and boosts immunity
46.	<i>Hibiscus rosa sinensis</i> L.	Malvaceae	Shrub	Flower	Medicinal, fodder, dye Hair fall, premature graying and dandruff
47.	<i>Ipomoea pes-caprae</i> (L.) R.Br	Convolvulaceae	Climber	Leaves	Medicinal, edible Rheumatism, arthritis, swelling and muscle pain

48. <i>Ipomoea sepiaria</i> J.konig ex Roxb	Convolvulaceae	Climber	Leaves	Medicinal, edible	PCOS and menstrual cramps
49. <i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Shrub	Seed	Medicinal, fodder	Swelling, reduce pain, scorpion stings and insect bites
50. <i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Acanthaceae	Shrub	Root	Medicinal, fodder	Malarial fever and viral infection
51. <i>Justicia diffusa</i> (Wild.) Nees	Acanthaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal, ornamental	Viral fever and chronic inflammatory diseases
52. <i>Justicia gendarussa</i> Mart. ex Benth.	Acanthaceae	Shrub	Root	Medicinal, fodder	Fever and viral infections
53. <i>Kalanchoe delagoensis</i> Eckl.& Zeyh	Crassulaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal	Burns, cuts and insect bites
54. <i>Lantana camera</i> L.	Verbenaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Medicinal	Eczema scabies and skin disorders
55. <i>Launaea sarmentosa</i> (Wild.) Kuntze	Asteraceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal	Liver health and jaundice
56. <i>Lawsonia inermis</i> L.	Lythraceae	Shrub	Leaves	Medicinal	Strengthened hair and dandruff
57. <i>Leucas aspera</i> (Wild.)	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaves and Flower	Medicinal, fodder	Antifungal, anti- inflammatory, antibacterial and analgesic properties
58. <i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i> L.	Solanaceae	Herb	Fruit	Medicinal	Neutralizing stomach acid and improving digestion
59. <i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves and Fruit	Medicinal	Diabetes, kidney stone and asthma
60. <i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	Leguminosae	Herb	Leaves and Root	Medicinal, dye	Wound, diarrhoea, piles and skin disease
61. <i>Mirabilis jalapa</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	Herb	Leaves and Flower	Medicinal, edible	Reducing fever, cough and pimples
62. <i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Climber	Fruit	Medicinal	Digestive issues, worm infestation and blood sugar levels
63. <i>Morinda tinctoria</i> Roxb.	Rubiaceae	Tree	Root	Medicinal, ornamental	Used for treating fevers, joint pain and detoxification
64. <i>Moringa oleifera</i> L.	Moringaceae	Tree	Whole plant	Medicinal, edible	UTI, regulate menstrual cycle and digestive issues
65. <i>Murraya koenigii</i> L.	Rutaceae	Tree	Leaves	Medicinal, fodder	Premature graying and dandruff
66. <i>Musa paradisiaca</i> L.	Musaceae	Tree	Whole plant	Medicinal, edible	Anaemia, kidney stone and wound healing
67. <i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	Apocynaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Oranmental	Eczema, scabies and ulcers
68. <i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal, edible	Cold, cough, bronchitis, indigestion and bloating
69. <i>Oldenlandia corymbosa</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Medicinal	Fever, liver disorders, and cancer treatment
70. <i>Oldenlandia umbellate</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Herb	Root	Medicinal, edible	Skin disease, menstrual irregularity and anaemia
71. <i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	Asteraceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal, fodder	Antimicrobial and wound healing properties
72. <i>Passiflora foetida</i> L.	Passifloraceae	Climber	Leaves	Medicinal, ornamental	Anxiety, mild epilepsy and nervous disorders.
73. <i>Pedaliium murex</i> L.	Pedaliaceae	Herb	Seed	Medicinal	Hormonal balance
74. <i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal	Kidney stone and UTI
75. <i>Physalis minima</i> L.	Solanaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal, fodder	Cold, cough and asthma symptoms
76. <i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Leguminosae	Tree	Leaves	Medicinal, ornamental, dye	Controlling Blood sugar level and insulin
77. <i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	Plumbaginaceae	Herb	Root	Medicinal, edible, dye	Arthritis, gout and rheumatism
78. <i>Polyathia longifolia</i> L.	Anonaceae	Tree	Bark	Medicinal	Strengthen heart and blood pressure
79. <i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Leguminosae	Tree	seed	Medicinal, edible	Healing wound, ulcers and fungal infections

80. <i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Myrtaceae	Tree	Leaves	Medicinal, ornamental	Diarrhoea, dysentery, indigestion and stomach pain
81. <i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Medicinal, edible	Arthritis, rheumatism and muscle pain
82. <i>Ruellia tuberosa</i> L.	Acanthaceae	Herb	Root	Medicinal, edible, timber	UTI and Kidney Stone
83. <i>Santalum album</i> L.	Santalaceae	Tree	Wood	Medicinal	Acne, pimples, sunburn and rashes
84. <i>Sida acuta</i> L.	Malvaceae	Shrub	Leaves and root	Medicinal, edible	Fever and boost immunity
85. <i>Sida rhombifolia</i> L.	Malvaceae	Shrub	Leaves and Root	Medicinal	Strengthen muscle and fatigue
86. <i>Solanum melongena</i> L.	Solanaceae	Herb	Root	Medicinal, edible	Inflammation, strengthen joints
87. <i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Solanaceae	Shrub	Leaves	Medicinal	Peptic ulcers and jaundice
88. <i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw	Solanaceae	Shrub	Fruit	Edible	Boost haemoglobin and Iron deficiency
89. <i>Solanum trilobatum</i> L.	Solanaceae	Climber	Leaves	Medicinal	Chronic cough, wheezing and asthma
90. <i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	Tree	Seed	Medicinal	Blood sugar level and insulin production
91. <i>Talinum portulacifolium</i> (Forssk.) Asch. ex Schweinf.	Talinaceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal, fodder	Anaemia and digestion
92. <i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Leguminosae	Tree	Leaves	Medicinal	Fever and body heat
93. <i>Terminalia catappa</i> L.	Combretaceae	Tree	Bark	Medicinal	Controlling Blood sugar
94. <i>Thespesia populnea</i> (L.) Sol ex Correa	Malvaceae	Tree	Leaves	Medicinal	Eczema and psoriasis
95. <i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L.	Zygophyllaceae	Herb	Root	Medicinal, edible, timber	UTI and kidney stones
96. <i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Asteraceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal	Infection and wound healing
97. <i>Wedelia trilobata</i> L.	Asteraceae	Herb	Leaves	Medicinal	Skin infection, ulcers

Fig. 1. Dominant families including the number of genera and species collected from Rajakkamangalam Beach

Family wise distribution shows that Solanaceae is a dominant family having 8 species under 5 genera. Acanthaceae, Amaranthaceae, Asteraceae, Euphorbiaceae and Leguminosae are the subdominant families which are including 6 species each. It is followed by Malvaceae, it includes 5 species and Rubiaceae which includes 4 species. The families such as Annonaceae, Apocynaceae,

Lamiaceae, Nyctaginaceae are include 3 species each. 7 families such as Anacardiaceae, Arecaceae, Convolvulaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Moraceae, Myrtaceae and Poaceae which consist of 2 species each. The remaining 24 families are represented by single species each (Fig. 1).

The most dominant genus is Solanum, it includes 4 species. It is followed by Justicia consists of 3 species. 7 genera consist of 2 species each and the remaining 79 genera are represented by single species each.

Indigenous uses

The present study reveals that the 97 plants collected from the study area are used for various purposes by the local people. Among the 97 plants 88 plants are used as medicine and 26 plants are edible. The plants are also used as fodder, ornamental, timber, dye, oil and Fibre as 14, 10, 7, 6, 1 and 1 species respectively (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Different indigenous uses of the plants from Periyakadu to Rajakamangalam beach

Medicinal uses

The present study recorded 88 plant species used for medicinal purposes by local communities. Various plant parts, including leaves, whole plant, roots, fruits, seeds, flowers, and latex, are employed in traditional remedies. Leaves were the most commonly used part (54 species), followed by Roots (18 species), Whole plant (16 species), Fruits (13 species), Bark (8 species), Flowers and seeds (5 species each) and Latex and Stem (2 species) each. The frequent use of leaves may be due to their easy availability and higher therapeutic potential. Overall, the findings indicate selective utilization of different plant parts depending on the ailments treated, with leaves forming the major component of herbal preparations, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Different useful parts of the medicinal plants from Periyakadu to RajakamangalamThurai beach

The present study reveals that different plant parts of 88 plants are used as medicine for various diseases such as poisonous bites, stomach disorders, fever, cold, cough, cuts, wounds, ulcers, kidney diseases, respiratory problems etc. Based on the information obtained from the indigenous people and the reviews all the ailments in the present study area were grouped into 15 categories.

Based on the information obtained from the traditional healers in the study area, all the reported ailments were categorized into 14 categories (Table 2) viz. gastro-intestinal ailments (GIA), dermatological infections/diseases (DID), respiratory systems diseases (RSD), genito-urinary ailments (GUA), fever (Fvr), skeleto-muscular system disorders (SMSD), poisonous bites (PB), circulatory system/ cardiovascular diseases (CSCD), endocrinal disorders (ED), liver problems (LP), Neurological Problems (NP), hair care (HC), cooling agents (CA) and general health (GH).

Several diseases were placed in one ailment category based on the body systems treated (Ayyanar and Ignacimuthu, 2011; Sukumaran *et al.*, 2021).

Most of the plants are used for treating Dermatological Infections/ Diseases (36 species), it is followed by Gastro-intestinal Ailments (25 species), Respiratory systems Diseases (28 species), Poisonous Bites (3 species), Genito-Urinary Ailments (16 species), Hair Care (6 species), Skeleto-Muscular System Disorders (21species), Fever (14 species), Liver problem (10) and Circulatory system/ Cardiovascular diseases (2 species each), Dental care (5 species), Endocrinal disorders (9 species), Neurological Problems (3), Cooling agent (1 species) and General health (8 species) (Table 2).

Most of the collected medicinal plants have efficiency to fight against more than one disease. For example *Psidium guajava*, *Pongamia pinnata*, *Leucas aspera* and *Ocimum sanctum* etc., are used to treat 4 diseases.

According to Trotter and Logan (1986), plants which are used in repetitive fashion in any ailment could be more likely to have biologically active component or pharmacologically active. Most of the plants reported in this study has good evidence of effectiveness and were scientifically validated as significant pharmacological agents. For example, *A. vasica* is one of the most frequently used medicinal plants among various indigenous communities all over the World for respiratory problems, especially cold, cough and

asthma and drugs with this plant has been used for a long period of time which does not has serious adverse effects (Claeson *et al.*, 2000), In support of our study, *P. amarus* has been scientifically proved to control hepatitis B and C viruses and possess hepatoprotective, immunomodulating and anti-inflammatory activity (Thyagarajan *et al.*, 2002). *A.*

indica, *Anacardium occidentale*, *C. viscosa*, *E. hirta*, *O. dillenii* and *M. pinnata* were used in the treatment of wound and related injuries by the Kani traditional healers and these plants showed significant wound healing and anti-inflammatory activity in experimental animals (Ayyanar and Ignacimuthu, 2009a).

Table 2. Ailments grouped by different categories in the present study area

Sl	Ailments categories	Biomedical terms	Tamil terms	No. of plants used	Total no. of plants
1	Gastro-intestinal ailments (GIA)	Acidity	Amilathanmai	1	25
		Indigestion	Cherimanaminmai	8	
		Bloating	Uppusam	2	
		Constipation	Malachickal	2	
		Diarrhoea	vayittuppokku	4	
		Dysentery,	Seethapethi	3	
		Stomach pain	Vayiru vali	1	
		Ulcer	Kudal punn	4	
2	Dermatological infections/ Diseases (DID)	Acne	Paru	1	36
		Pimples	Mugapparu	3	
		Sunburn	Venkuru	1	
		Rashes	Thadippukal	1	
		Wounds	Punn	13	
		Cuts	Vettukayankal	1	
		Skin infection	Charuma thottu	2	
		Eczema	Karappan	3	
		Scabies	Chirangu	2	
		Fungal infection	Poonchai thottu	2	
		Leprosy and ringworm	Thozhu noi and padar thamarai	1	
		Skin diseases	Charuma viyathikal	5	
		Warts, Ringworm	Marukkal and Padar thamarai	1	
3	Respiratory systems diseases (RSD)	Asthma	Ellupunooi	8	28
		Cold	Salli	4	
		Cough	Irumal	11	
		Bronchitis	Moochukulalalarchi	4	
		Wheezing	Iluppu	1	
4	Genito-urinary ailments (GUA)	Kidney disorders	Cirunirakakolaru	8	16
		Menstrual problems/Menorrhagia	Matavidaimikaippu	1	
		Piles/Hemorrhoides	Moola nooi	2	
		Urinary disorders	Cirunirakakolaru	5	
5	Fever (FVR)	Fever	Kayccal	11	14
		Malaria	Muraikayccal	1	
		Dengue fever	Dengue kaichal	1	
		Viral fever	Virus kaichal	1	
6	Skeleto-muscular system disorders (SMSD)	Body pain	Udal vali	3	21
		Headache	Thalaivalli	1	
		Rheumatism	Vathanooi	1	
		Swellings	Veekam	2	
		Inflammation	Veekam	4	
		Muscle cramps	Thasai pidippu	1	
		Arthritis	Mudakku vatham	5	
		Joint pain	Moottu vali	4	
7	Poisonous bites (PB)	Scorpion sting	Thekkoduku	1	3
		Insect bite	Poochikadi	2	
8	Circulatory system/ Cardio vascular diseases (CSCD)	Heart diseases	Ithayanoykal	2	2

9	Endocrinal disorders (ED)	Diabetes	Neerilivu nooi	8	9
		Hormonal balance	Utchurappu neer samanilaiyinmai	1	
10	Hair care (HC)	Anti-dandruff	Thalaipoduku ethirpu	3	6
		Hair fall, premature graying	Mudi uthirthal and Naraithal	3	
11	Cooling agent (CA)	Body cooling	Udalkulichii	1	1
12	Liver problems (LP)	Jaundice	Mancal kamalai	2	10
		Liver disorders	Kalliralkolarukal	4	
		Detoxification	Nacchu veliyettuthal	4	
13	Neurological problem (NP)	Anxiety	Pathattam	1	3
		Deep sleep and reduce stress	Aazhntha urakkam and mana azhutham	2	
14	General health (GH)	Anaemia	Eratha sokai	5	8
		Antiseptic	Kirumi Nasini	1	
		Fatigue	Sorvu	2	

The ethnomedicinal studies evidently pointed out that, instead of trying to identify the active components and pharmacological actions of plants through massive collection of plants from natural sources, it is better to start investigating the efficacy of the plant based on their use in folk medicine, since most of the commercially proven drugs used in modern medicine were initially tried in crude form in traditional or folk healing practices (Fabricant and Farnsworth, 2001).

CONCLUSION

Biodiversity is a part of our daily lives and livelihoods and constitutes the resources upon which families, communities, Nations and future generations depend. Human society from the very beginning of its appearance on this earth has been indispensably associated with the plant kingdom for its Survival. Plants provide our basic food crops, building Materials and medicines.

So far only about ten percent of Plants have ever been evaluated for their medicinal or Agricultural potential and so there are certainly many new Drugs and new crops yet to be discovered.

The noteworthy findings stand out from this work, data suggests that people in the more isolated village know and consume more plants than people in the more accessible village. Conservation and judicious utilization of this coastal plant wealth is important because they have become threatened by over-exploitation. The findings of this study reveal

that common plant species seen around us also play an important role in the treatment of various ailments. Due to the impact of urbanization, partial Modernization and over exploitation of plant species for medicinal purposes there is chance for disappearance of some plant species in near future. Therefore, appropriate measures should be taken to conserve these plants for healthy and disease-free life.

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